

The Role of Technological Innovation and Social Capital in Maintaining Businesses Sustainability of SMEs

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Abstract

Nowadays, the challenges faced by SMEs (Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises) in the era of globalization are increasingly complex and competitive. A deep understanding of innovation and technology is needed, which is one of the important factors in building a strategy that can create competitive advantage and sustainability of SMEs. In addition, good strategic leadership and management are also needed that provide clear guidance on how SMEs can manage social capital in accordance with local wisdom so that it can continue to be accepted and in accordance with the nation's culture. To analyze this, this paper uses a systematic review method that examines 20 literatures on the role of innovation and technology in the business world. The results of the analysis show that innovation and technology also have an important role in helping SMEs maintain business sustainability in this era of globalization. Therefore, strategic leadership and management are needed along with social capital adaptation to support the implementation of innovation and technology in SMEs, especially in utilizing opportunities and facing challenges caused by free trade or globalization.

Key words: SMEs, Technological Innovation , Social Capital, Business Sustainability

1. Introduction

Since the Republic of Indonesia's independence, the Indonesian nation has experienced significant developments in the fields of innovation and technology. The concepts of innovation and technology have become the center of attention in efforts to improve the efficiency and productivity of the economic sector in the country. However, in its development, social capital, such as: local wisdom, geographical factors, government systems and market economies also influence the process of implementing innovation and management technology in Indonesia, especially in the current era of globalization. Some of the influential local cultural values include: mutual cooperation, tolerance, kinship, sympathy and respect for superiors or those who are older in society. Thus, the development of the business world in Indonesia is a process

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of adaptation and integration of social capital, namely between traditional markets and free markets (global).

The free market caused by globalization is the most significant and influential megatrend, both positive and negative. Its impact is also accompanied by innovations in information technology and social media communication. This megatrend shows the magnitude of the impact of globalization on the business world, cultural values, education, technology, and the economic sector. This results in social change, such as migration and internationalization. Another example is that the increasing amount of knowledge and information obtained through social media can have a good or bad impact on changes in organizational behavior and human capital (Johnson, 2022). It has a bad impact if the innovation and information are directly applied in an organization without going through a filtering process first.

According to Prasetyo (2019), personal values or human capital change differently in relation to globalization. In other words, social and economic changes are reflected in the relationship between value systems and changes in globalization. The relationship between globalization and changes in other aspects of life depends on the character of society and the culture of society. People or communities with stronger characters can maintain their values better and longer than those who do not. The development of globalization over time is a certainty faced by humans and society in various aspects of their lives, especially in thinking, behaving, and communicating. Globalization involves human values, economic values, socio-cultural values, and politics as well as organizational identities that lead to global exchanges that form a global trade culture or free market.

In this case, Adam Smith expressed the economic theory of competitive free market efforts in his book entitled TMS (The Theory of Moral Sentiments) in 1759 and WON (Wealth of the Nations) in 1776. According to him, a free market is an effort that can regulate its own economic activities. Its main focus is how to improve the quality of individuals through simplicity and good economic behavior, such as saving and investing, trade and division of labor, education and capital formation, and the use of new innovations and technologies. His thinking is greatly influenced by the natural law tradition, which also greatly influences his thinking in the fields of morality, economics, politics and jurisprudence, especially regarding free market justice and the role of government.

Adam Smith's theory of invisible hands is a modern economic theory that supports free markets because it is considered to be able to protect individual freedom and rights (markets). This is also related to how sympathy can influence human actions and relationships with others in their efforts to achieve life goals. Adam Smith's thinking was also influenced by the Stoics who argued that these magical hands are a natural order that inspires and directs the development of society in an orderly and harmonious manner with its natural surroundings. According to him, this invisible hand is none other than the personification of Divine wisdom. Adam Smith believed that God would work behind the economic stage (which is invisible) to realize human welfare and happiness, through the activities or efforts of each individual who is willing to tolerate and sympathize with one another.

Thus, the theories contained in Adam Smith's free market concept are based on the harmonious movement of the universe, where a free market must be created to realize justice and guarantee the natural freedom of humans. Sympathy and tolerance must be sought to regulate individual interests in order to maintain common interests and achieve the common good. So it must be distinguished between freedom from (freedom from) and freedom for (freedom for). What is meant by 'freedom from' is freedom from mercantilism and monopoly. This freedom is binding because it aims to limit the selfishness of each individual. While 'freedom for' is the freedom to create a common good based on human freedom to fulfill their own interests (self interest). This freedom is natural and occurs like a harmonious order of the universe. In other words, a free market or globalization is a cosmic order that allows each individual to pursue their interests and thus ultimately realize what is the goal of the free market itself. Where in this order every individual will get a great opportunity to pursue their interests and the free market will improve the condition of everyone, because in this case the free market functions under natural law or what according to Adam Smith's theory is under the principle of justice, especially the principle of not harming others.

The development and adaptation of Adam Smith's management theory also affect business units and economic sectors in Indonesia. In this case, one of the rapidly growing business units is SMEs (Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises). SMEs have an invisible role (invisible hands) but have a significant role in the economic system of a country, including in Indonesia. This is because SMEs can create new jobs, expand income distribution, and create economic equality. In general, although SMEs face various major challenges caused by globalization, there are still many opportunities open for SMEs to develop by utilizing technology and innovation appropriately. Likewise, if empowered with strategic planning and social capital, SMEs will make a positive contribution to the national economy.

In this case, the biggest challenges faced by SMEs in the era of globalization include: increasingly tight market competition caused by the entry of new products from abroad, so that SMEs must continue to improve the quality of their products, and the advancement of technology and digitalization which requires SMEs to be able to adapt and master the latest technology and utilize digital platforms in order to survive (Zhao & Zhang, 2022). The opportunities that can be utilized by SMEs in the era of globalization are gaining easier access to the global market through online sales and marketing, reaching consumers around the world without the need to have a physical store, and increasing opportunities to innovate and improve the quality of products and services by learning from foreign competitors.

In order to maximize opportunities and overcome challenges in this era of globalization, SMEs need to implement or integrate innovation and technology in their operational activities in order to maintain the sustainability of their businesses. In this case, the main idea of technological innovation for SMEs is to utilize advanced technology and innovative strategies to improve operational efficiency and drive business growth. In other words, the focus of innovation and technology management integration is to provide solutions and implement innovative management practices to create competitive advantages.

Based on the background, the researcher is interested in conducting research using the Systematic Review method to examine the role of innovation and technology management in maintaining the sustainability of SMEs in the era of globalization. Through this paper, it is expected to provide a simple contribution and review that can help national business actors and SMEs to continue to advance in developing innovation and technology theories in the midst of global trade competition. The discussion of this paper also combines Adam Smith's economic philosophy and social capital as a global corporate culture that is expected to remain in line with the ideology of the Indonesian nation; 'Bhinneka Tunggal Ika', which aims to realize a just and prosperous society.

Method

This paper uses a systematic review research method. A systematic review is a research methodology that analyzes a study or phenomenon by collecting and evaluating one or several previous studies that are related and focused on the topic or phenomenon being discussed. The stages of analysis in the systematic review method consist of: determining the topic or phenomenon to be discussed, determining the data search strategy or information source, selecting studies through quality assessment according to research criteria, and data analysis (Triandini et al., 2019). The literature sources used in searching for previous research articles related to this study are sourced from Google Scholar and Scopus Journal.

The selected literature is in the form of scientific journals in English and can be accessed in full text. The publication year for the selected scientific journals is between 2000 - 2025. Where the discussion in the scientific journal includes the implementation of innovation and technology in the business world. The number of scientific journals analyzed based on these criteria is 20 scientific journals, both published nationally and internationally. All of these articles are used as sources of literature in this study. The output of data extraction is in the form of a table consisting of the name of the researcher, year of publication, research title, research findings, and the relationship between the findings and the topic or phenomenon being discussed.

3. Analysis and Discussion

Table 1 below presents the results of a review of previous scientific research journals that analyze the role of innovation and technology with social capital in relation to the continuity and resilience of MSME business ventures.

Authors	Title	Key Finding	Finding Related to UMKM
Giada Di Stefanoa, Alfonso Gambardella, Gianmario Verona (2012)	Technology push and demand pull perspectives in innovation studies: Current findings and future research directions	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. highlights the role of demand as a source of innovation. 2. competencies enable firms to match technology to demand and leverage technology and demand as sources of innovation. 3. there is a distinction between external and internal sources of innovation. 	Sources of innovation can be purely external or internally generated competencies that enable SMEs to integrate external knowledge in an effort to improve operational efficiency and increase competitiveness.
Ngoc Khuong Mai, Thanh Tung Do and Dieu Trang Ho Nguyen (2022)	The impact of leadership competences, organizational learning and organizational innovation on business performance	<p>Results-oriented competencies that have a significant impact on business performance.</p> <p>Organizational learning is influenced by all three leadership competencies, while only cognitive and interpersonal competencies positively influence organizational innovation. In addition, the research findings emphasize the mediating role of organizational learning and organizational innovation in the relationship between leadership competencies and business performance. Organizational learning and organizational innovation also act as mediators in the relationship between cognitive competencies and business performance.</p>	The relationship between SMEs and innovation and technology can improve the following: operational efficiency, creating access to global markets, adapting to market changes, increasing competitiveness, so that in the end it can build the sustainability and resilience of SMEs.
René Rohrbeck, Hans Georg Gemünden (2011)	Corporate foresight: Its three roles in enhancing the innovation capacity	<p>Three roles that a company must play to maximize its innovation capacity:</p> <p>(1) the role of strategist, who explores new business areas;</p>	Through innovation, SMEs can increase operational efficiency, foster collaboration and partnerships as part of social capital, improve

	of a firm	(2) the role of initiator, who increases the number of innovation concepts and ideas; and (3) the role of challenger, who challenges innovation projects to improve the quality of their output.	output quality, so as to increase competitiveness and build MSME sustainability.
Eleonora Pantano, Milena Viassone (2014)	Demand pull and technology push perspective in technology-based innovations for the points of sale: The retailers evaluation	This analysis shows the high interest of retailers in innovation. The analysis shows that the decision to invest in innovation underlines the technological limitations of retailers. For technology-based innovations, retailers show a critical approach in the adoption modality. Therefore, there is a very poor diffusion that does not meet consumer expectations.	Through innovation and technology, SMEs can increase operational efficiency, foster collaboration and partnerships, support decision-making and strategic planning to build MSME sustainability and resilience.
Elena Cefis, Riccardo Leoncini, Luigi Marengo & Sandro Montresor (2023)	Firms and innovation in the new industrial paradigm of the digital transformation	This study investigates how companies are facing digital transformation from three different perspectives, looking at its determinants, its development patterns, and its technical-economic impacts. The various theoretical backgrounds, data sources, empirical methodologies, and the originality and managerial/policy relevance of the research results make this special issue a unique perspective to investigate the new industry paradigm.	Through innovation and technology, SMEs can increase operational efficiency, accelerate decision-making and strategic planning.
Frank W. Geels (2002)	Technological transitions as evolutionary reconfiguration processes: a multi-level perspective and a case-study	This results in a multilevel perspective on Technological Transitions, in which two views of evolution are combined: (i) evolution as a process of variation, selection and retention, (ii) evolution as a process of development and reconfiguration.	The relationship between SMEs and technology is to increase operational efficiency and accelerate decision-making and strategic planning to build MSME sustainability.
Md. Nurun Nabi and Zhiqiang Liu (2022)	Investigating the effects of	Dynamic capabilities of knowledge management significantly mediate between leader management behavior and radical innovation.	Innovation can help SMEs in adapting to market changes and improving decision-making and

	leaders' stewardship behavior on radical innovation: a mediating role of knowledge management dynamic capability and moderating role of environmental uncertainty	Similarly, environmental uncertainty substantially moderates the relationship between knowledge management dynamic capabilities and radical innovation, especially when the intensity of environmental instability increases—decreases, the management behavior of leaders and adherents of knowledge management dynamic capabilities tend to enhance radical innovation performance.	strategic planning through strategic leadership roles, as part of the organization's social capital.
Adner and Kapoor (2016)	Innovation ecosystems and the pace of substitution: Re-examining technology S-curves'.	Understanding the rate of technological substitution requires a joint consideration of the evolution of new and old technologies. And understanding this evolution requires an examination of the interdependencies within the broader ecosystem of components and complements in which the focal technology is embedded.	Through innovation and technology, SMEs can adapt to market changes and foster collaboration and partnerships with other parties.
Caihong Liu, Hannah Ji, Jonah Ji (2022)	Mobile information technology's impacts on service innovation performance of manufacturing enterprises	This paper presents findings suggesting that MIT has a direct impact on a firm's service innovation capability (SIC) and service innovation performance (SIP). Specifically, SIC continuously drives the growth of SIP in a firm, and thus acts as a mediating factor. Furthermore, the results show that both SIC and SIP vary with the strength of the innovation network in each firm, while the moderated mediation effect of SIC remains constant.	Through innovation and technology, SMEs can improve operational efficiency, increase competitiveness and build business sustainability and resilience.
Karin Högberg and Sara	Strategic Responses to Digital Disruption in	The findings of this study indicate three overall organizational responses to DDI, including:	The contribution of digital innovation to SMEs includes expanding the existing literature on digital

Willermark (2022)	Incumbent Firms– A Strategy-as Practice Perspective	1) relating to the new digital business environment; 2) strategies translated into practice; 3) renegotiated values.	strategies and responses to digital disruption and providing implications for the practice of increasing MSME operational efficiency and
Giada Di Stefano, Alfonso Gambardella, Gianmario Verona (2012)	Technology push and demand pull perspectives in innovation studies: Current findings and future research directions	First, this study focuses more on the role of demand as a source of innovation. Both describe how competencies enable firms to match technology to demand and leverage technology and demand as sources of innovation. The third reveals the difference between external and internal sources of innovation. The sources of innovation can be purely external or internally generated competencies that enable the firm to integrate external knowledge within its boundaries.	Through innovation and technology, SMEs can increase operational efficiency, adapt to market changes, assist in decision-making and strategic planning in accordance with the organization's social capital, and increase competitiveness in order to build MSME sustainability and resilience.
Yuan Ma, Guisheng Hou, Qiyue Yin, Baogui Xin, Yajun Pan (2018)	The sources of green management innovation: Does internal efficiency demand pull or external knowledge supply push?	Green management innovation is driven by external knowledge supply, while internal efficiency demand does not play a significant role. In addition, green management innovation has a positive effect on the economic performance of the firm and the demand for internal efficiency moderates its effect.	Through innovation and green management which are part of social capital, SMEs can increase operational efficiency, financing and green investment, so as to build the sustainability and resilience of SMEs.
Aleš Levstek, Andreja Pucihar, and Tomaž Hovelja (2022)	Towards an Adaptive Strategic IT Governance Model for SMEs	This paper presents an empirical evaluation of the main ITG mechanisms from the literature which clearly shows that some mechanisms are not universally but situationally required, thus indicating the need for a new contingency-based ITG model.	SMEs need innovation and technology in decision making and strategic planning based on existing social capital to build business sustainability and resilience.
M. Nuñez-López (2014)	The dynamics of technological change under	For internal innovation, the presence of residual resources in the case of full	SMEs need innovation and technology to facilitate access to long-term

	constraints: Adopters and resources	adoption does not necessarily lead to competitive exclusion. In contrast, with external innovation, existing technologies cannot be replaced. There is persistence of closely related technologies and competitive exclusion in renewable energy technologies and TV sets.	financing and investment and increase competitiveness in order to build business sustainability and resilience.
Chaogai Xuea & Yawen Xub (2017)	Influence Factor Analysis of Enterprise IT Innovation Capacity Based on System Dynamics	Industrial cooperation, IT personnel, and enterprise R&D investment have different effects on IT system development capability at different times, and IT system development capability plays an indirect role between IT resources and IT innovation capacity, and is explored by the internalization of IT resources.	SMEs need innovation and technology to facilitate access to social capital, resources and investment to build business sustainability and resilience.
Remigiusz Kozłowski, Marek Matejun (2011)	Dynamic Business Environment as a Source of Technology Entrepreneurship Development– A Case Study	The function of the environment in the field of technological entrepreneurship development can be explained through five roles: research & development, mobilising, financing, promotional & systems.	Environmental innovation and technology can help SMEs in terms of increasing operational efficiency, reducing costs and optimizing resources and facilitating access to financing and investment.
Sainan Zhao, Yichao Zhang (2022)	Dynamic Influence of Digital and Technological Advancement on Sustainable Economic Growth in Belt and Road Initiative (BRI) Countries	The increase in EGDI (E-government Development Index), ICT (information and communications technology) exports, and the growth of internet users have a significant and positive influence on sustainable economic growth, which leads to the fact that digital and technological progress has a positive influence on sustainable economic growth.	Innovation and technology can help SMEs adapt to market changes and build business sustainability and resilience.
Supriyo Das, Amit Kundu, Arabinda Bhattacharya (2020)	Technology Adaptation and Survival of SMEs: A Longitudinal Study of	The results show that both institutional capabilities and external capabilities become significant when time is used as a selection variable. The high significance of the time variable indicates the dynamism of	Technology can help SMEs adapt to market changes and build business sustainability and resilience.

	Developing Countries	the current technological environment.	
Eun-Hwa Seo, Choo-Yeon Kim and Kwangsoo Kim (2020)	A Study on the Mechanisms Linking Environmental Dynamism to Innovation Performance	Our study finds that, there is a causal interdependence between the mediators, both strategic prospects and the strategic prospects–absorptive capacity combination mediate the relationship between environmental dynamism and innovation performance.	Innovation and SMEs have a relationship in efforts to increase operational efficiency and decision making and strategic planning.
Sharon Beder (2000)	The Role of Technology in Sustainable Development	Sustainable development depends on technological change to achieve its goals, where there is a role for governments in taking the difficult steps necessary to force radical technological innovation.	Technology can help SMEs to adapt to market changes, social capital, and improve decision-making and strategic planning.

Based on the analysis results presented in Table 1, it has been shown that integrating technology and innovation is very beneficial for business actors including SMEs. This integration is important for survival and growth in competitive conditions in this era of globalization. Innovation and technology provide tools to operate efficiently, while innovation drives competitive advantage and long-term success. By utilizing both of these, SMEs can improve the efficiency of their operational activities, serve their customers better, and remain adaptable to rapidly changing global market conditions, but remain environmentally friendly (Ma, 2018). Therefore, in order to maintain the operational sustainability of SMEs, strategic management and innovation are needed in producing their goods and services. SMEs must be able to maintain and develop a national strategic management system that is supported by social capital and is in line with the nation's culture and global market developments (Cefis et al., 2022). The following are some examples of strategic management implementations that can be applied by SMEs in facing globalization, namely:

1. Digitalization and e-commerce, namely by developing a digital platform to sell their products online. This will open up the market more widely and increase brand visibility (Cefis et al., 2023), (Gemünden, 2011).
2. Leadership training and human resource development as part of the organization's social capital. This is necessary so that both leaders and employees can have knowledge and skills that are relevant to the needs of the times, especially in the field of technology and digital marketing in global trade (Mai & Nguyen, 2022).
3. Collaboration with the Government and other SMEs, in terms of training, investment and socialization of regulations that can grow social capital and support SMEs (Beder, 2000).

Strategic management supported by a spirit of kinship and sympathy can support the empowerment of social capital, human resources and natural resources that are more just and have an Indonesian perspective. In other words, every human being comes from society, and society is shaped by the environment, culture, science and management systems. All of these things, although they continue to evolve, still lead to a system of management and strategic leadership (Das & Bhattacharya, 2020). In this case, strategic leadership and strategic management which are part of social capital will help members of an organization including SMEs to adapt and remain competitive and survive in an ever-changing environment through the role of a leader.

Overall, although SMEs face major challenges due to globalization, they also have many opportunities to grow with the right use of social capital, technology, digitalization, and innovation. If empowered properly, SMEs can become important actors in the ever-growing global economy. However, SMEs also need to maintain social capital in the form of values contained in local culture (local wisdom), such as tolerance, mutual cooperation, kinship, and sympathy, because these local cultural elements are part of social capital that is still very relevant and strategic for the development of strategic management systems in Indonesia. This is like Bonnici's opinion which states that strategic management is defined as a process of evaluation, planning, and implementation created to maintain or increase competitive advantage (Mjaku, 2020).

The following are some positive impacts of the integration of strategic management with technological innovation and social capital for SMEs in the era of globalization as presented in Table 1, namely:

a. Improving Operational Efficiency

Innovation and technology can help SMEs simplify their operational activities, allocate resources more efficiently, and increase productivity, making them more competitive against larger companies.

b. Building Sustainability and Resilience

Innovation and technology enable SMEs to produce environmentally friendly and energy-efficient processes and products, maintain social capital, monitor and improve sustainability practices, so that SMEs can be more responsible, attract consumers who are aware of the environment and local cultural values.

c. Improved Decision Making and Strategic Planning

Innovation and technology help SMEs remain flexible and responsive to changes in global demand and competition and enable SMEs to make better decisions in real-time and in line with social capital. This has resulted in more planned and relevant business strategies to the complexities of the global market.

d. Adaptation to Market Changes

Technology innovation and management can help SMEs anticipate market trends and customer behavior, allowing businesses to adapt quickly but remain relevant to global market needs.

e. Increasing Competitiveness

Innovation and technology management will help SMEs in production, distribution, and marketing by using new innovation technologies, so that SMEs can offer high-quality, unique,

and competitively priced products and services. This is especially important in a global economy where they compete not only with local entrepreneurs but also with international companies.

f. Fostering Collaboration and Partnership

Innovation and technology management will enable SMEs to collaborate with external parties both from within and outside the country, so that it can help SMEs to develop new products and solutions, form partnerships and alliances with other businesses (social capital) in the global market.

g. Access to Financing and Investment

Innovation and technology can help SMEs find easier access to alternative forms of financing, such as crowdfunding or peer-to-peer lending, thus enabling SMEs to access social capital and global investment opportunities that were previously limited to large companies only.

The application of strategic business management in leadership and resource management in supporting SMEs in the free market era is an aspect that can increase human capital and social capital (Johnson, 2022). Social capital that is right on target and used strategically to create a comprehensive information structure will provide easy access for business people (SMEs) in facing the challenges caused by globalization. This is because they can receive the right business information, including good and bad news about the organization on an ongoing basis. On the other hand, social capital can also increase the efficiency of SMEs and help them in making strategic and innovative decisions to solve common problems in accordance with corporate culture and local wisdom values. This happens because social capital can foster a sense of mutual trust in social relationships to realize common interests (Kozłowski & Matejun, 2011).

In this case, strategic leadership is a leadership style that prioritizes and is oriented towards the future. Strategic leadership will focus on continuously improving the strategic management process (Mjaku, 2020). A strategic leader will be able to anticipate all possibilities while maintaining flexibility but still maintaining social capital, thinking innovatively and being able to collaborate with other parties to achieve better changes, create competitive advantages and maintain the sustainability and resilience of the company (Nabi & Liu, 2022). In this era of globalization and rapidly changing international trade, leaders or MSME business actors are faced with choices that require making the right and fast business decisions based on information that is believed to be an innovation and leads to progress.

Conclusion

The integration of innovation and technology with strategic management and leadership has enabled business actors or SMEs to manage social capital and resources more effectively, develop strategic leadership, and create a conducive, innovative and productive work environment amidst global competition. In other words, all these efforts will help SMEs in formulating business strategies to face challenges and open up new opportunities caused by globalization in order to maintain the sustainability of their business efforts.

Some examples of the benefits of strategic leadership, social capital, global corporate culture and human resource management integrated through innovation and technology for SMEs include: sharing information and resources, providing assistance both financially and non-financially, establishing and maintaining relationships between SMEs, and creating a harmonious MSME community. Therefore, there are three important things from technological innovation and social capital that can be applied in the business world or SMEs, namely: bonding, bridging, and linking between SMEs in order to formulate innovation and technology strategy management to face challenges and take advantage of opportunities caused by globalization in order to realize operational sustainability and resilience.

In addition, a strategic leader also has the ability to sort out information or data that is right or wrong, relevant or otherwise. This ability will make strategic leadership an important element in achieving the success and sustainability of SMEs. Strategic leadership can help SMEs to maintain financial stability in both the short and long term, maintain social capital, and maintain the sustainability of MSME operational activities, as well as create optimal economic growth. In other words, strategic leadership creates the design and implementation of successful innovation and business management strategies (Mjaku, 2020). Therefore, strategic leadership designs a vision and mission for the organization and encourages its implementation through innovation and technology to achieve business sustainability and resilience. Innovation and technology are an evolution of human history that continues to process and change for the better in accordance with the times.

In this case, there are three important elements of strategic leadership that need to be considered by SMEs in the era of globalization, namely: social capital, local cultural values, and beliefs. Beliefs are the core of a culture that is held firmly by leaders and employees. Members of an organization or employees in a company must have certain beliefs, but they also adhere to local cultural values that are recognized by society. Values are cultural standards for distinguishing what is reasonable and fair in corporate decision making. Values are also dynamic, so they vary over time and between groups and collective cultures.

Based on the results of the analysis of 20 literatures (scientific journals) selected and analyzed using the systematic review method, the findings in this paper clearly show that innovation and technology play a very positive role in the development and sustainability of Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) especially in the current era of globalization. In the era of globalization, technology and innovation are very important for the continuity and growth of MSME businesses. By adopting new technologies and fostering a culture of innovation, SMEs can increase efficiency, expand social capital networks, engage customers more effectively, and remain competitive in facing the challenges of globalization. For SMEs, embracing technology and innovation is not just a choice, but a necessity in order to continue to develop in a global economic system or a free market that is interconnected and continues to move rapidly.

In general, SMEs that have innovative business strategies will be superior in terms of competitiveness and are able to survive in various situations. Implementation of strategies and human resource management based on social capital is the main key for MSME businesses to remain relevant and competitive in facing global market changes. SMEs that successfully

integrate technological innovation and investment with social capital will be able to create a conducive, innovative, and highly competitive work environment. In practice in the field, these factors have supported the sustainability and resilience of MSME businesses as a whole in various situations and conditions.

Therefore, the suggestions that can be given to SMEs in formulating business strategies related to innovation and technology in the era of globalization are as follows:

1. Developing a sustainable strategic leadership development program that supports innovation and technology.
2. Implementing a global corporate culture system and social capital through innovation and technology processes to improve performance and ensure business continuity.
3. Implementing digital technology in human resource management to accelerate adaptation to global market changes.
4. Building an effective communication system between SMEs so that they can share information and knowledge about innovation and technology.
5. Increasing investment and competitiveness in both local and global markets, especially in the field of innovation and technology. This is necessary so that the quality of the products and services they produce meets market needs and can compete in global trade.

Finally, as there is a proverb that says "A journey of a thousand miles begins from a single step", then no matter how difficult and long the journey that we will or have taken, it certainly requires a starting point or beginning to start it all. As business people need to change and take steps to seize opportunities. All changes or opportunities must have intentions and goals that will help us achieve what we hope for in this life. Likewise with the theory of innovation and technology that we discuss in this paper. Business people and SMEs must be dare to innovate, take the right technology strategy and develop existing social capital so that they can grow and survive both in national and international trade.

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